

Implementation of Universal Education Theory (UE)

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Abstract:

The objective of the research was to assess the main sources needed for the implementation of Universal Education Theory (UE). Nowadays, with the current curriculum, nations are not satisfied; a significant portion of our society's youth and adults are jobless, smokers, addicted, nervous, and hopeless, whether in India, South Africa, Ethiopia, Brazil, England, Germany, or the USA. The real solution would be a non-optional revision of the National curriculum, tertiary education curriculum and the implementation of Universal Education Theory for future generations to come and so that equip in their minds and learn moral education, ethics and able to build their nations from corruption free, unethical practices.

Keywords: Universal Education Theory, Universal Education Theory (UE), Implementation of Education Theory, Moral Education, Morality, Ethics, Corruption, Eradication, National Education, Tertiary Education,

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Introduction

The thesis: The implementation of Universal Education Theory discovers a new hope for the staggering world of education by uncovering the ingredients of a morally built education and academia seeking a more developed, peaceful, and wisdom-dominated society. The author of Universal Education Theory, Prof. Dr. Rejaul Abedin, has been evaluated by my personal and online academic global groups in previous research to have a higher academic intelligence, along with extreme creativity and imagination, which he is politely applying towards a more educated, corruption-free, highly developed, and peaceful world.

The thesis shall cover educational policy, individual preparedness for skill and wisdom development, the most educated versus the least educated countries, resources, strengths, gaps, global response, and evaluation from a research-based questionnaire, discussions, results, and conclusions. Moreover, it will delve into world health professionals whose backgrounds are also based on education.

Methodology:

The methodology applied in this research was mixed. The response was predominantly from various universities, Global Peace and Development Associations, and the Global Federation of Universities, Colleges, and Seminaries WhatsApp platform, which included calls and messaging, as well as a few face-to-face conversations. A total of 200 people including policy makers, politicians, religious leaders, business men and women, school directors, professors, students, and parents were invited, out of whom only 120 responded and participated. Female participants comprised 32%, and male participants comprised 68%. Respondents answered a 10-question questionnaire. Every question had five choices: A to E, where A (strongly disagree) = -10, B (disagree) = -5, C (neutral) = 0, D (agree) = +5, and E (strongly agree) = +10 scores.

Discussion

In recent years, schools across America have cut back on the arts, leaving some students without any music instruction. However, in 2014 study, involving hundreds of children from low-income homes, researchers found that music lessons can help such kids improve their literacy and linguistic skills. According to Dr. Nina Kraus, a neurobiologist at Northwestern University, research has shown that there are differences in the brains of children raised in impoverished environments that affect their ability to learn. While more affluent students do better in school than children from lower income backgrounds, she found that musical training can alter the nervous system to create better learner and help offset this academic gap. Music lessons seem to strengthen the ability of the nervous system to handle noise in a bustling atmosphere, such as a schoolyard. Because of this improvement in brain functioning, the children may develop better memory and a greater ability to focus in the classroom setting, which will help them to communicate better. (2019, Mikkola H. & Nugmanova M., *Global Education Management*, p. 10)

I could perceive from the above statement that music in schools influences not only their memory capability and learning skills but their future:

1. Communication
2. Concentration, and
3. Mental abilities

Moreover, it is my personal belief that children should grow happy and comfortable throughout their educational life and at home.

What is Universal Education Theory

Universal Education Theory was developed by Prof. Dr. Rejaul Abedin in the hope of seeing a better, more peaceful, and developed world in which students develop into whole persons (physically, emotionally, mentally, spiritually, socially, and economically) through an integrated curriculum that incorporates talents, self-learning, experience, and morals (religious beliefs).

$$UE = [HV + (EA + EST) + MR] - Ie$$

Where, UE

UE = Universal Education.

HV = Human being as an Individual who requires Value addition.

EA = Education from Academic sources.

EST = Education from Self Learning and Talent from Almighty Allah (SWT).

MR = Morality / Moral Education from Religion.

Ie = Eradication of all Evils from individual character (Individual Evils)/ Eradicating the evils of corruption.

Objective of the Research:

The significance of “**Universal Education Theory (UE)**” for grooming up morality through Education - Universal Education Theory (UE) is ensured by a theory or formula system of learning morality or ethics or moral education from any religion. As it is proved that all religion heavenly tells human being, do the right things avoid wrong or unethical ones.

As a result of the implementation of Universal Education Theory (UE) in academic stages, the possible significance may outcomes which mentioned below:

- * Removes egoism, lust, anger, greed, pride, attachment, covetousness from individual and group life
- * Reduces biases, nepotism, corruption and violence.
- * Develops value to the human personality.
- * Promotes ethical sense of human beings.
- * Expands human power, goodness, and principles.
- * Eradicates ignorance and enlighten all countries and nations.

(2019, Rejaul A., PhD., FCMAN, Volume: 1, Issue: 1, IJARBAS, Implementation of Universal Education Theory in global education system towards the development of individual, teams, society and prevention of corruption, p. 3). Regarding this an alternative Citations may be retrieved from The Digital Library of Commons, Indiana University Libraries and ERIC – ED.GOV by Institute of Education Sciences Database.

In The Universal Education Theory, I would like to replace "Almighty Allah" with "Almighty Creator" in representing EST shown in the formula. All ethnic groups mostly believe that they have a creator but give Him as many names as there are vast languages on this globe. Moreover, since we are concerned about universality, we have to use universal representation.

A. Scope and areas of “Universal Education Theory (UE)”

There are huge scope and numerous areas available where Universal Education Theory can be utilized, the few of them are mentioned as follows:

Primary School level.

- High Secondary School level.
- College level (11 and 12 classes).
- University (Undergraduate level / Degree level).
- University (Post graduate level / Master level).
- Vocational training stages.

Universal Education Theory (UE), that prepares young and adult pupils for life, the workforce and the society and that aims to reduce injustice, discrimination, extremism, gender, social class, racism & ethnicity in every phases of life, encourage to practice morality in political life, social life, and promote individual learning through ethically and to develop inner mind & students able to show respect to the other community people and religions and so on.

B. Benefits of Value Addition through Training and Development for Individuals and Teams, and Society

We all know that value addition via academic and other sources is an individual thing. Making an individual progress relies on a whole range of influencing factors and students or learners make progress at different times of their life and at different rates.

Here the concept of “Value addition” actually indicates where the individual quality enhancement made by a person or group of people to any area required by the concerned individual(s) in order to exchange these quality and good deeds with others through money or without any exchange value.

Individual values: Individual values reflect how a person show up in his or her life and their specific needs-the principles s/he live by and what they consider important for their self-interest. Individual values include: enthusiasm, creativity, humility and personal fulfillment.

Value addition to develop personal value can be made through many ways as for example, it could include:

- * Participation in the In-house training
- * Participation in the academic programs
- * Participation in the religious moral education
- * Attending in the On-the-job learning (In terms of employee)
- * Mentoring Advice on specific area
- * Individual study or self-learning using online or offline study materials
- * Eradication of all Evils from individual character (Individual Evils)

C. Education from Academic Sources

"Academic Education" is generally defined as education which has learning as its primary purpose. Several institutions and educational systems have equated academic with "University" but this is not always the case.

(2019, Dr. Rejaul A., Volume: 1, Issue: 1, Implementation of Universal Education Theory in global education system towards the development of individual, teams, society and prevention of corruption, p. 4)

I realize that the main actors in facilitating the process of implementing the theory are policy makers, curriculum designers, professors, students, and parents. The policy makers should be convinced that the government's investment in education has a guaranteed return by enhancing moral, social, economic, and technological advancement.

Motivation influences achievement, but what influences motivation? Student motivation is complex; many variables influence whether students engage and persist in tasks, including teacher, parent, and cultural beliefs (Wigfield & Eccles, 2000). Students' beliefs about their own competence and whether they have any control over the outcome of a task, as well as their interest in the task and the reason why they are interested, also influence student engagement and persistence (Bandura, 1986; Covington, 1992; Pintrich & Schrauben, 1992; Pintrich & Schunk, 2002). In this chapter, we focus on two strategies that are related to motivation: reinforcing effort and providing recognition. These two strategies affect one or more of the following student variables:

* Self-efficacy: belief about one's competency.

* Control beliefs: beliefs about one's ability to influence what is happening or will happen.

* Intrinsic motivation: motivation that comes from an individual's desire for self-satisfaction or pleasure in completing the task rather than from an external source, such as a reward.

* Task value: beliefs about reasons for doing a task.

(2012, Ceri B. Dean, Elizabeth R. Hubbell, Howerd Pitler, Bj Stone, Classroom Instruction that Works 2nd Education. pp. 20 - 21)

I have realized, from the above statement, that internal motivation for learning plays a vital role thus I would recommend courses such as: theology, sociology, moral, self-awareness, self-confidence, general psychology, life skills, physiological for every student before tackling complex college level courses or programs.

Providing students with opportunities for self and peer assessment speaks to these 21st century skills. By allocating time for students to reflect upon their own learning and to give and receive feedback from peers, we help them develop skills they will need throughout their K-12 years, in college, and in the work place. The tools available now (e.g., survey tools, blogs, wikis)strongly amplify students' and teachers' abilities to access, collaborate, and get feedback on their work. Encouraging students to use the many sources available online and through social media and engage in the feedback process helps them become self-directed learners. (2012, Ceri B. Dean, Elizabeth R. Hubbell, Howerd Pitler, Bj Stone, Classroom Instruction that Works: 2nd Education. p.17)

I observe as stated above that a student who is given the opportunity to evaluate himself or herself, or is assessed by his or her peer group, is enabled to reflect, collaborate with lecturers, peers, and society at large, and develop abilities. This is true: if students hate their teacher, they also hate the courses that are taught by that particular teacher. It is also my personal belief that a student's general health, family situation, economy, and morals play a significant role in their motivation for learning.

In 2020 the world was rocked by the Covid-19 pandemic. The rapid spread of a microscopic virus drastically much of the world's way of life, separating us from our friends, neighbors, and families and taxing our individual psychological fortitude to the extreme. Quarantines drove people into their homes, and social distancing rules prevented most forms of socializing: restaurants shut down, work place closed. Almost overnight, online video calls and social media become many people's only connection to the outside world. It was like a massive global experience in both social isolation and the nature of life online.

As weeks of lockdown stretched into months, online tools began to fill the void left by a lack of real-world interaction. Remote meetings kept many businesses afloat and allowed schools and universities to keep their (virtual) doors open. Religious services were held online. Even weddings and funerals were conducted virtually.

I realize from the above statement about the school situation during the Covid-19 pandemic that communication technology played a vital role in lessening the harm. This can be taken as a lesson, and rigorous preparation should be done for any undefined future pandemic.

During my teaching years at Saint Joseph's School and Professional Institute, I realized that each student's participation, even coming out in front to hold the position of the lecturer and explain their ideas, boosts their confidence greatly and leads to better results than just observing, reading, and sitting for an exam.

This year, I acquired a new license through self-study and challenge. The exam was online under strict camera supervision. To pass that license exam, I first downloaded PDF manuals relevant to the subject, read them, attended videos and associated the material with real phenomena in the field. I discussed concepts with experienced professionals when the situation allowed, repeated similar exams, challenged myself, and observed that I needed to focus on the strategies of field examiners. Despite bad weather and some physical pain, I was determined and disciplined because I knew the license would be a life changer. I relaxed and sat for the exam, responding with a focus on the objectives of the ministry – I won by scoring 93%. I applied the Universal Education Theory! You may ask how; I have a strong belief that I shall win in the end, learned through self-search, discussions with friends, and inquiries with professionals, associating theories with practical situations in the field.

If we accept the wisdom—and more recently the scientific evidence that our relationship really are among our most valuable tools for sustaining health and happiness, then choosing to invest time and energy in them becomes vitally important. And an investment in our social fitness isn't only an investment in our lives as they are now. It is an investment that will affect everything about how we live in the future. (2023, Robert W., MD, Marc S., PhD., *The Good Life: Lessons from the world's longest scientific study of happiness – Create a more meaningful and satisfying life.* p. 116)

I perceive from the above statement that searching for wisdom, through implementing universal education theory would enable communities and societies to live a meaningful and happy life.

Instruction Planning: Creating the environment for learning

Instructional planning begins with focused attention on creating a productive environment for learning. The three categories of strategies included in this component of the framework include

- Setting objectives and providing feedback
- Reinforcing efforts and providing recognition
- Cooperative learning

These strategies are foundational because they involve the articulation of what students will learn, how their learning will be evaluated, and how closely they pay attention to the affective aspects of learning. When teachers do not attend to the latter, students motivation often suffers, causing students to miss out on opportunities to acquire a range of skills that help them be lifelong learners and productive workers and citizens. (2012, Ceri B. Dean, Elizabeth R. Hubbell, Howard Pitler, Bj Stone, *Classroom Instruction that Works 2nd Edition.* p. 153)

I realized from the above statements that high concentration and work of research must be done on setting learning objectives, student evaluation criteria, and promoting life-long learning.

Students will need resilience and a growth mindset to overcome the kinds of challenges that such rapid shifts create. They need to see these changes as opportunities to frame the dynamic nature of the future workforce as an opportunity to grow and flourish rather than find themselves behind or obsolete. A vital component of that growth mindset will likely come from developing a habit of continuous learning with a strong sense of curiosity and a desire to stay relevant through the pursuit of knowledge.

Students must also see themselves as problem solvers to approach complex problems that AI cannot solve with creativity and persistence. They will need to both have the self-confidence that they can take ownership of their lifelong journey and a collaborative mindset so that they seek feedback and learn from others. (2023, Priten S. AI and the future of education, Teaching in the Age of Artificial Intelligence, pp. 43-44)

As discussed above, I observe that students confidence should grow beyond modern AI in solving complex puzzles; moreover, own life-long learning drive and cooperate with other members of society in seeking knowledge and wisdom.

Figure 1. East Saint Paul Public Library: Well-organized and updated facilities, starting from kindergarten to tertiary education, facilitate learning and professionalism. (Photo by author)

Figure 2. Free parks in downtown Saint Paul offer residents the opportunity to enjoy walking, socializing, reading, and marketing on some occasions, which contributes to their vitality and happiness. (Photo by author)

Figure 3. Minnesota offers modern economic apartments for college students, and tenants that lessen stress in the urban areas where life is paycheck to paycheck. (Photo by author)

Figure 4. MSP Airport offers online ticketing and fast travel options for visiting college students, professors, researchers & scientists, incorporating all in-house services and professionals: acupuncture doctors, pharmacy stores, clothing markets, restaurants, relaxation centers, emergency resting facilities, up-to-date showers, and Wi-Fi, etc. (Photo by author)

Figure 5. An efficient public transportation system in Saint Paul, Minnesota, USA enables every customer to get to their destination, whether it be a school, college, hospital, airport, or train station, every ten minutes. (Photo by author)

Figure 6. Centers: Art and Science for skin, hair, dental care are growing globally (Photo by author)

Natural healthcare centers do have their own contributions to research and improving society's healthy way of living.

Medical doctors per 10,000 population in the world 2021

Figure 7. Medical doctors per 10,000 population reported by World Health Organization (<https://www.who.int/data/gho/data/indicators/indicator-details/GHO/medical-doctors>) (reported year 2021, issued year 2025)

I perceive from the figure above that Australia, Northern Europe, Russia, and the USA have relatively more medical doctors to meet the population's healthcare demands than the rest of the world. As the report in "The World Health Organization - World Health Statistics 2021" indicates, a tenfold increase in the number of medical doctors may not satisfy the current healthcare demand. Thus, the implementation of Universal Education Theory could lead to training a huge number of professionals in the near future.

Figure 8. Snow often hinders transportation, school activities, affects laborers, and health in Northern Hemisphere (Photo by author)

Figure 9. Winter weather blocks children from playing in their fields and exposes their bodies to sunlight, which affects their vitality in various ways. Thus, replacement tablet vitamins are consumed. (Photo by author)

Number	Most educated country	Completed tertiary education
1	South Korea	69.29%
2	Canada	66.36%
3	Japan	64.81%
4	Luxembourg	63.12%
5	Ireland	62.88%
6	Russia	62.09%
7	Lithuania	57.48%
8	United Kingdom	57.47%
9	Netherlands	55.6%
10	Norway	55.03%

Table 1. 10 Most Educated Countries: Higher rate of Completed tertiary education (source/database info: www.wisevoter.com, dated 2023)

Most Educated Countries versus Rate of Tertiary Education Completed

Figure 10. Most Educated Countries versus rate of Tertiary Education completed (Chart by author)

As indicated in the tables and charts: South Korea is the most educated country, whereas Afghanistan is the least educated country. The implementation of Universal Education Theory shall balance the gap.

The most educated countries are mostly located in the northern hemisphere where the weather is extreme and harsh for approximately six months per year. I personally appreciate the societies there for their success in education tolerating all life obstacles.

Number	Most educated country	Completed tertiary education
1	Afghanistan	3.1%
2	Senegal	2.8%
3	Madagascar	2.8%
4	Mauritania	2.5%
5	Burkina Faso	2.1%
6	Mozambique	1.8%
7	Uganda	1.7%
8	Mali	1.6%
9	Niger	1%
10	Burundi	0.9%

Table 2. Last Educated Countries: lower rate of completed tertiary education (source/database info: www.wisevoter.com, dated 2023)

Figure 11. Last Educated countries (Chart by author)

The last educated countries are mostly located in the Southern Hemisphere. The favorable weather and natural resources could boost education, but this potential has not yet been realized. The most educated have the obligation to uplift and bring the least educated countries to their level in order to observe the implementation of Universal Education Theory.

The intrinsic factors of teaching specifically concern teaching tasks. According to Dinham and Scott (1998), this domain crosses schools and specificities of locale and broadly affects teachers' perceptions. Examples of this domain that could be cited include working with the students, preparing lessons, colleagues' collective work, and seeing students learn and develop. In that way, studies point out that many sources of job satisfaction are related to working directly with students in classrooms and to the actual tasks related to it (Guarino, Santibañez & Daley, 2006). Reinforcing that, for Ma and MacMillan (1999), evaluation of teachers is often based on affective or subjective judgments of how successfully they meet the instructional tasks and objectives in classrooms.

Following that idea, many studies have looked at the intrinsic aspects of the profession, presenting elements of satisfaction and dissatisfaction. In that domain, competence and

autonomy within teachers' tasks are the two most significant predictors of satisfaction and retention (Albert & Levine, 1988). Toropova, Myrberg and Johansson (2020) suggests that teachers who better evaluate their self-efficacy tend to have higher levels of job satisfaction. In the same direction, Sims (2020) analysed that the teachers who feel competent because they have had the proper training for their everyday tasks are more likely to stay in their careers and are more satisfied. The same is reported regarding teachers' autonomy within their tasks. Teacher autonomy addresses the freedom to select teaching methods and strategies that align with the teacher's pedagogical beliefs and values (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2014). Research shows that teachers who experience high levels of autonomy in their job also perceive more satisfaction (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2009; 2010; Sterns et al., 2015; Zembylas & Papanastasiou, 2006). Moreover, Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2010) point out that teachers' autonomy is negatively related to emotional exhaustion and burnout syndrome. Conversely, empirical work shows that programs and job demands that diminish teachers' sense of autonomy and competence harm their perception of satisfaction (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2009; Fernet et al., 2013). (2022, Jose Q., *Teachers' perception of their job-satisfaction in private schools in São Paulo municipality*, Department of Education, Regent's Park College, Oxford University, p.12)

I perceive from the statements mentioned above that not only policy makers, students, parents, directors, and presidents are responsible for ensuring the implementation of Universal Education Theory, but teachers are also considered an integral part of the mission.

Results

The results were amazing: 89.2% positively responded to the implementation of Universal Education Theory, indicating that nations are almost fed up with the current curriculum and calling for change. A U.S. resident female parent, Participant 1, responded with a high score of 95%. She has a son attending high school and a daughter who will graduate from George Washington University with a bachelor's degree in accounting next year. Her daughter has been competitive and won a scholarship of ninety thousand dollars per year. Participant 2, a male second year computer science student at Minnesota University responded with 90% score; participant 3, a female Indian religious and worship organizer, responded with 95% score. Doctor A, a male South African sociologist, responded with a score of 100%; Doctor B, a male senator from California, also responded with a score of 100%, while Doctor C, a male online lecturer, from West Africa responded with 2 B's, 1 D, and 7 E's, scoring 70%. Meanwhile, the remaining 10.8% negatively responded to the implementation of Universal Education Theory; this latter group has been possibly satisfied with the current curriculum and educational policy. The research results indicate that the implementation of Universal Education Theory has been highly favored.

Conclusion:

Implementation of Universal Education Theory (UE) by Prof. Dr. Rejaul Abedin can be realized by preparing and applying a sound curriculum which comprises moral, talents, self-learning, and experience of an individual. The revising of all National and Tertiary Education Curriculum shall be predictable, in the near future, to meet the Universal Education Theory objectives.

Future Implications and Limitations:

All nations shall necessarily apply Universal Education Theory (UE) and harness the benefits associated with it: wisdom, effectiveness, peace, health, economic development, spiritual advancement, skills, and knowledge. More research should be done in creating a link, which I could not accomplish here, among all government sectors and authorities under UN or UNESCO, European Commission and facilitate the implementation.

References:

2012, Ceri B. Dean, Elizabeth R. Hubbell, Howerd Pitler, Bj Stone, *Classroom Instruction that Works 2nd Education*

2019, Dr. Rejaul A., Volume: 1, Issue: 1, P 1-11, IJARBAS, *Implementation of Universal Education Theory in global education system towards the development of individual, teams, society and prevention of corruption* <https://www.ijarbas.com/2019/08/03/implementation-of-universal-education-theory-in-global-education-system-towards-the-development-of-individual-teams-society-and-prevention-of-corruption/> And

Digital Library of Commons, Indiana University Libraries, USA

<https://dlc.dlib.indiana.edu/dlc/items/be38ec35-f3e1-46b0-ba62-33cc4d6d0a9a>

ERIC – ED.GOV by Institute of Education Sciences Database

<https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Corruption&ff1=subMoral+Values&ff2=autAbedin%2C+Rejaul&id=ED597150>

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2025, *World Health Organization*, international data reported 2021

<https://www.who.int/data/gho/data/indicators/indicator-details/GHO/medical-doctors>

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Appendices:

The questionnaire has been the same for curriculum developers, policymakers, supervisors, directors, students, parents, and professors: participants and respondents are mainly global, and WhatsApp is applied as the best medium.

Instruction: Select appropriately. Each number has the following representation.

I arranged this five-point scale:

A. Strongly disagree = -10

B. Disagree = -5

C. Neutral= 0

D. Agree = +5

E. Strongly agree= +10

Questionnaire

1. Skills such as critical thinking, problem solving, ICT should be taught in schools
A. strongly disagree B. disagree C. neutral D. agree E. strongly agree
2. A school should have qualified and certified Teachers and professors
A. strongly disagree B. disagree C. neutral D. agree E. strongly agree
3. There should be regular monitoring and evaluation of Teachers, and professors
A. strongly disagree B. disagree C. neutral D. agree E. strongly agree
4. Students should get career guidance and counseling services
A. strongly disagree B. disagree C. neutral D. agree E. strongly agree
5. Parents should be actively involved in school activities to realize Implementation of Universal Education Theory
A. strongly disagree B. disagree C. neutral D. agree E. strongly agree

6. Participatory teaching method should be applied in schools and colleges to promote Universal Education Theory

A. strongly disagree B. disagree C. neutral D. agree E. strongly agree

7. In Implementation of Universal Education Theory the challenges teachers and professors face in delivering quality education shall be lessened as curriculum revised, students are shaped in moral, actively participating, and parents contribution

A. strongly disagree B. disagree C. neutral D. agree E. strongly agree

8. Implementation of Universal Education Theory positively affect students' academic performance because students have moral, facilities and resources; moreover, actively participating in classes

A. strongly disagree B. disagree C. neutral D. agree E. strongly agree

9. Universal Education Theory ensures a better school management

A. strongly disagree B. disagree C. neutral D. agree E. strongly agree

10. Implementation of Universal Education Theory would significantly improve the overall education quality

A. strongly disagree B. disagree C. neutral D. agree E. strongly agree

